

Development of a Dual-Fluorescent Biosensor for Real-Time Quantification of (p)ppGpp and GTP Dynamics with AI-Based Single-Cell Analysis of the Stringent Response in *Escherichia coli*.

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Background:

The stringent response is an important regulatory mechanism in bacteria that enables adaptation to nutrient deprivation and other stress conditions such as antibiotic exposure. In *Escherichia coli*, this response is primarily mediated by the enzymes RelA and SpoT, which synthesize the alarmone nucleotides guanosine tetraphosphate and pentaphosphate, known as (p)ppGpp (Potrykus & Cashel, 2008).

The accumulation of (p)ppGpp causes many changes inside the cell by decreasing the amount of GTP. GTP is needed both as a basic building block for (p)ppGpp production and as a molecule that initiates the transcription of certain RNAs essential for bacterial growth.

GTP serves as both a molecule for (p)ppGpp synthesis and a critical molecule for initiating transcription at certain promoters, especially those controlling ribosomal RNA and amino acid synthesis genes. When GTP levels decreased, the cell reduces the production of RNA and amino acids. This helps the bacteria save energy and focus on surviving stressful conditions (Dalebroux & Swanson, 2012; Gourse et al., 2018).

Although the stringent response has been studied extensively, the exact timing, such as how long it takes between the start of nutrient limitation, the rise in (p)ppGpp levels, and the drop in GTP, is still not clearly understood. Creating a genetically encoded biosensor that can measure both (p)ppGpp and GTP at the same time in living cells would help reveal how this stress response is controlled and how bacteria quickly adjust to changes in their environment. (Hauryliuk et al., 2015).

Objectives:

- 1- To make a dual-fluorescent reporter biosensor in *E. coli*:
 - GFP under the control of a GTP-sensitive promoter: **rrnB P1**, which is downregulated when GTP levels drop. I chose the **rrnB P1 promoter** because its activity is strongly dependent on GTP levels, making it a reliable indicator of GTP depletion during the stringent response (Gaal et al., 2001; Paul et al., 2004).
 - RFP under the control of a (p)ppGpp-responsive promoter **rmf**, which is activated upon (p)ppGpp accumulation. I chose the **rmf promoter** because its transcription is directly activated by the accumulation of (p)ppGpp during the stringent response, making it a specific indicator of alarmone-mediated stress signaling (Izutsu et al., 2001).
- 2- To assess the dual-reporter biosensor under induced stringent response conditions in both wild-type and *relA/spoT* mutant strains.

- 3- To measure the response time of the (p)ppGpp biosensor by time-lapse fluorescence microscopy, and that's by observing GFP and RFP fluorescence over time after amino acid starvation, accounting for the maturation time of fluorescent proteins to accurately determine the onset of promoter activation.
- 4- To compare the kinetics of the stringent response between single cells and populations, in order to demonstrate the diversity in cellular response.
- 5- To improve data accuracy, using AI to quickly analyze images, find when promoters turn on, and see how cells respond differently.

Hypotheses:

🌱 wild-type *E. coli* : amino acid starvation activates (p)ppGpp synthesis via RelA/SpoT

This leads to a rapid decrease in GFP (Green Fluorescence Protein) signal,

At the same time, RFP (Red fluorescence Protein) signal increases as (p)ppGpp activates the target promoter **rmf promoter**.

🌸 relA/spoT mutants: (p)ppGpp is not produced efficiently:

GFP signal remains high (rrn promoter active), and RFP does not increase.

This serves as a negative control and confirms specificity of the biosensor.

Methodology

1- Promoter Selection and Cloning:

Clone the rrnB P1 promoter upstream of GFP.

Clone a (p)ppGpp-responsive promoter rmf upstream of RFP.

2- Plasmid Construction:

- Design a single plasmid vector containing both fusion GFP and RFP.

- Include origin and antibiotic resistance marker.
- Transform plasmid into E. coli Wild type and *relA/spoT* mutants.

3- Induce the stringent response via:

- Amino acid starvation

- We will use time-lapse fluorescence microscopy to know the response time of the (p)ppGpp biosensor and that's by observing the expression pattern of the fluorescent reporters **GFP** and **RFP** in live bacterial cells.

- Inducing the bacterial cell into stringent response by subjecting them to amino acid starvation, leading to the accumulation of (p)ppGpp and activation of the biosensor promoter.
- fluorescence images were captured at specific intervals every 5 min for 5 hrs using a fluorescence microscope, and to ensure accuracy in determining the biosensor's response time, the maturation time of GFP and RFP was accounted for by applying a correction factor, thereby allowing us to estimate the true timing of promoter activation rather than the delayed appearance of fluorescence.
- Artificial Intelligent (AI) will be used to enhance the image analysis, using a cellpose model, pre-trained on fluorescence microscopy datasets, to detect and quantify fluorescence intensity across time points. The AI system enabled for the following:

Data Analysis:

The fluorescence cells images will be captured every 5min for 5hrs. Using the cellpose Ai model will be used to segment each individual cell and to measure their fluorescence intensity over time.

The intensity data for wild-type and mutant strains will be analyzed separately to compare their response dynamic. The following plot is the final expected results of the Data analysis

Interpterion of the plot:

- **Transparent thin lines:** Individual cell fluorescence intensity curves, showing variability between cells.
- **Thick lines:** The average fluorescence response for each strain wild type and Mutant:
 - Blue** = Wild-type
 - Red** = Mutant
- **Dashed vertical lines (--):** Response onset time (when the fluorescence starts to rise above baseline).
- **Dotted vertical lines (::):** Peak time (when the fluorescence reaches its maximum value).

Expected Outcomes:

- A validated dual biosensor system capable of real-time monitoring of the stringent response in *E. coli*.
- Precise measurement of the time gap between stress induction and response signaling.
- Showing that the decrease in GTP happens before or at the same time as the increase in (p)ppGpp.
- Demonstrating how individual cells respond differently in how fast and how strongly they react

Significance:

- The biosensor provides a flexible tool that doesn't disrupt the cells, and real-time to study bacterial stress responses.
- This system can be adapted to analyze drugs that disrupt early stress signaling, potentially blocking bacterial persistence.
- This system can be extended to study stress responses in other bacteria or used for various purposes in synthetic biology.

References:

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